

CEPHALOMETRIC FACIAL SOFT TISSUE ANALYSIS AMONG PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENT SKELETAL CLASSES IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

Prof Dr Syed Shah Faisal¹, Aroosa Najam², Syed Sheeraz Hussain³, Dr Samia Siraj⁴,
Syeda Afshan Jamal⁵, Dr Anam Aijaz⁶

¹Professor of Orthodontics Karachi Medical & Dental College Karachi Metropolitan University

²Bds, Fcps resident Orthodontics department Karachi Medical and Dental College Karachi Metropolitan University, Karachi, Pakistan

³Professor & Head of Orthodontics, Head Dentistry, Karachi Medical & Dental College

⁴BDS, MCPS (orthodontics) Assistant professor Department of orthodontics Karachi Medical and Dental college, Karachi Metropolitan university

⁵dental officer Karachi Medical and Dental college, Karachi Metropolitan University

⁶Demonstrator Karachi medical and dental college Karachi metropolitan University

¹shahorthodontist@gmail.com, ²uroosa.najam@gmail.com, ³drsheerazhussain@gmail.com,

⁴samiasiraj09@gmail.com, ⁵drafshan57@gmail.com, ⁶anamaijaz1986@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17431952>

Keywords

Article History

Received: 03 September 2025

Accepted: 11 October 2025

Published: 24 October 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Prof Dr Syed Shah Faisal

Abstract

Objective: To use cephalometric radiographs of our population to identify the features of the soft tissues of the face in skeletal class I, II, and III patients.

Methodology: This cross-sectional study was carried out at the Karachi Medical and Dental College's Department of Orthodontics in Karachi, Pakistan. Ninety-six participants' lateral cephalograms were traced, and based on the ANB angle, they were categorized into skeleton classes I, II, and III. Eight linear and five angular soft tissue measurements were taken. The cephalometric soft tissue properties of the various skeletal classes were compared using the chi-square test and independent t-test; a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: The percentage of people in class I, class II, and class III was 48.1 percent, 48.1 percent, and 3.8 percent, respectively. There was no statistically significant relationship between the variables when skeleton classes were compared to different age groups, genders, and lip skills ($P > 0.05$). Age, soft tissue profile angles, and z angles were found to be statistically significantly correlated with the means of skeletal classes and age, angle parameters, and soft tissue profile ($p < 0.05$). The mean values of age, angles, and soft tissue profile were also compared by gender. The findings showed a significant relationship between soft tissue properties and age.

Conclusions: In relation to the various skeletal classes I, II, and III, cephalometric radiographs are crucial diagnostic indicators for the soft tissues of the face.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main goals of orthodontic therapy is to create a beautiful, aesthetically balanced facial profile with harmonious soft tissue proportions.(1) Beauty has always been a topic of attention for all cultures, despite the fact that it has evolved significantly over time.(2) The soft tissues of the face are essential for speech, facial appearance, and other physiological functions. Because the force generated by the perioral soft tissue can change tooth position and malocclusion, a comprehensive evaluation of the soft tissue profile is essential for diagnosis, treatment planning, post-treatment stability, and success.(3) Riedel states that the assessment of soft tissue profiles is significantly influenced by the relationship between the incisors and their bony base as well as the pattern of facial growth.(4)

Examiners favor a more retrusive lip position for a lower convexity in both genders in order to enhance facial aesthetics.(5) Individual characteristics like age, gender, race, and nutritional status might induce differences in soft tissue thickness.(6) According to a study done at the Children's Hospital in Lahore, women's profiles are somewhat more convex than men's.(7) Furthermore, a Saudi Arabian study found that women have greater soft tissue face plane angles and Z angles than men.(8)

Another study found that for both genders, the soft tissue depth at the labrale inferius point was lower in Class III and higher in Class II.(9) Cephalometric radiography is most frequently utilized in orthodontic practice to assess and examine each patient's soft tissues. Individualized standards can be set to maximize facial beauty based on the patient's soft tissue features and conventional facial qualities.(7) Hence, no study of this kind has been carried out in Pakistan that has assessed the soft tissue features of the face in relation to the three skeletal classes of orthodontic patients. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to use cephalometric radiographs to interpret and

analyze various linear and angular variables of face soft tissues in skeletal Class I, Class II, and Class III male and female Pakistani patients.

METHODOLOGY:

The Karachi Medical and Dental College's Ethical and Scientific Review Committee gave its approval to this cross-sectional study. Following the subjects' written agreement, data were collected from 96 patients' pre-treatment lateral cephalograms at Karachi Medical and Dental College's Department of Orthodontics. Participants who fulfilled the requirements for inclusion were enlisted. This group included Pakistanis of both sexes, aged 12 to 30, who had never had orthodontic treatment before and who showed clear visibility of all necessary parameters on a lateral cephalometric radiograph.

Patients having a history of trauma, cleft lip or palate, facial asymmetries, craniofacial malformations and syndromes, orthodontic therapy, or facial plastic surgery were excluded. Using acetate paper sheets and an illuminator, lateral cephalograms were manually retraced. Patients will be categorized into skeletal Classes I, II, and III based on the measurement of the ANB angle, which will determine the skeletal classes. Based on the landmarks that were discovered, 13 variables, five angular and eight linear measurements, were measured using soft tissue analysis. Every measurement will be noted on a proforma that has already been created.

SPSS version 22 will be used for statistical analysis. Age and parameter means and standard deviations will be computed. To adjust for effect modifiers like age and gender, stratification will be used. Soft tissue properties in various skeletal classes of malocclusion will be compared using the post-stratification ANOVA test. A P value of less than 0.05 will be considered significant.

Figure 1. Cephalometric tracing

Figure 2. Linear and angular measurements on cephalometric

RESULTS

According to Table 1, the percentage of people in classes I, II, and III was 48.1%, 48.1%, and 3.8%, respectively. The relationship between skeleton classes and various age groups, genders, and lip abilities was assessed using chi-square. The findings showed that there was no statistically significant difference between the variables (P

>0.05). Table 2. The means of skeletal classes and age, angle parameters, and soft tissue profile were compared using the independent t-test. In terms of age, soft tissue profile angles, and z angles, the results were significant ($p < 0.05$). Table 3. Likewise, a mean comparison of soft tissue profile, age, and angles was done by gender. The findings indicated that age and soft tissue profile had a significant impact. (Table 4)

Table 1: Frequencies (%) of individuals in Class I, II and III

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Class-I	51	48.1	48.1	48.1
	Class-II	51	48.1	48.1	96.2
	Class-III	4	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total	106	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Association of skeletal class I, II and III with Age groups, Gender and Lip Competency

		skeletal Class						P Value
		Class-I		Class-II		Class-III		
		Count	Column Valid N %	Count	Column Valid N %	Count	Column Valid N %	
Age Group	<=20 years	35	68.6%	39	76.5%	2	50.0%	0.419
	>20 years	16	31.4%	12	23.5%	2	50.0%	
Gender	Male	16	31.4%	22	43.1%	1	25.0%	0.413
	Female	35	68.6%	29	56.9%	3	75.0%	
Lip competency	Competent Lips	27	52.9%	31	60.8%	2	50.0%	0.700
	Incompetent Lips	24	47.1%	20	39.2%	2	50.0%	

Table 3: Mean comparison of skeletal classes with age, angle parameters and soft tissue profile

Skeletal Class		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Age (years)	Class-I	51	18.0000	4.73286	.003
	Class-II / III	55	17.2909	3.37020	.003
Nasolabial Angle	Class-I	51	92.4706	15.59404	.496
	Class-II / III	55	94.7273	18.21320	.494
Soft tissue profile angle	Class-I	51	159.3137	7.40943	.048
	Class-II / III	55	156.4364	7.36046	.048
Full soft tissue profile angle	Class-I	51	129.4118	6.34721	.019
	Class-II / III	55	126.5091	6.15802	.019
H angle	Class-I	51	19.5686	4.50002	.409
	Class-II / III	55	20.3727	5.40509	.406
Z angle	Class-I	51	67.1451	8.61729	.005
	Class-II / III	55	62.0091	9.57838	.004

Table 4: Mean comparison of Gender with age, angle parameters and soft tissue profile

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value	
Age (years)	Male	39	18.6923	4.66315	.041
	Female	67	17.0149	3.59078	.057
Nasolabial Angle	Male	39	94.9487	19.75235	.547
	Female	67	92.8806	15.21315	.575
Soft tissue profile angle	Male	39	157.0513	7.30518	.422
	Female	67	158.2687	7.61295	.418
Full soft tissue profile angle	Male	39	126.0513	6.70800	.022
	Female	67	128.9851	5.98354	.027
H angle	Male	39	20.5256	5.08991	.397
	Female	67	19.6716	4.93100	.402
Z angle	Male	39	63.4744	10.25013	.405
	Female	67	65.0657	8.96987	.423

DISCUSSION:

Understanding the soft tissues that cover the face and how they are affected by many aspects, such as the skeletal relationship and the soft tissue thickness⁶, is essential to achieving an attractive facial appearance. This study examined the soft tissue facial profile for class I, II, and III occlusion in a sample of adult Pakistanis, which makes comparisons to other studies challenging because of variations in the variables tested or sample size. The current study's findings indicated that there was no significant difference between males and females in terms of Z angle, H-angle, or nasolabial angle; nevertheless, there was a notable mean difference between the sexes in terms of age and soft tissue profile. Conversely, a prior study⁸ showed that, while not statistically significant, women had a larger Z-angle than men in every course. In every group, the labiomental angle was considerably larger for females than for males. All groups indicated a substantial difference in the nasolabial angle between males and females. The results of the current investigation demonstrated how accurate landmark location is. There were significant standard deviations in the occlusal, maxillary, mandibular, palatal, and nasolabial angles. Similar findings were obtained in a study of male Caucasian Americans.^(10, 11) Since the considerable standard deviations indicated that these data had a high degree of

individual variability, it was proposed that comparisons be made using a variety of normal values instead of the mean.⁽¹²⁾

Our research revealed that the soft tissue profile was convex, with a H angle of $19.5^\circ \pm 4.5^\circ \text{SD}$. The experiment yielded H angle values that were exactly the same as those reported by Basciftci⁹. According to Merrifield¹⁰, adults have a larger Z angle than adolescents. For children aged 11 to 15, the average Z angle was $78^\circ 5'$, and the Z angle values were higher for girls than for boys. This investigation's average Z angle ($67.1^\circ \pm 8.6^\circ \text{SD}$) was significantly lower than Merrifield's result.⁽¹³⁾ Class II patients exhibited a more convex profile, with a Z-angle of $62.0 \pm 9.5 \text{SD}$, while class I patients had a Z-angle of $67.1 \pm 8.6 \text{SD}$. The Z-angle of males is $65.0 \pm 8.9 \text{SD}$, while that of females is $63.4 \pm 10.2 \text{SD}$.

According to Ricketts, the top lip of adult females should be 4 mm posterior to the aesthetic plane, while the top lips of men should be somewhat retracted.⁽¹⁴⁾ He concluded that in males, the lower lip should be located 2.0 mm posterior to this line. The internal angles between the soft tissue Nasion, Subnasale, and Pogonion points were referred to as soft tissue profile angles in the current study.

Since a relaxed lip posture does not need muscular compensation to identify dentoskeletal anomalies, Arnett and Gunson recommend it for assessing

the soft tissue profile.(15) It was also used in a recent studies to standardize the acquisition of cephalograms for precise assessment of soft tissues.(16, 17) In order to precisely measure the soft tissue thickness, cephalograms were taken in the relaxed lip position for this investigation. Patients receiving orthodontic or prosthodontic therapy were not included in this study since these procedures may change the soft tissue profile. According to age, men's soft tissue was significantly thicker than women's. In none of the skeleton classes were gender differences found to be statistically significant.(18) In terms of labrale superius, labrale inferius, pogonion, and menton thickness, Uysal et al. found statistically significant gender differences.(19) Studies examining soft tissue cephalometric norms for several groups with varying median ages have found that these parameters were statistically significantly more significant in males than in females.(15, 16, 20)

CONCLUSION:

For determining the link between the different skeletal classes I, II, and III and the soft tissues of the face, cephalometric radiographs are essential diagnostic tools. During the diagnostic and treatment planning stages of orthodontics or corrective jaw surgery, various skeletal malocclusions can be identified. Because of bone malocclusions, the soft tissue thicknesses of men and women vary greatly with age.

REFERENCES:

1. Turley PK. Evolution of esthetic considerations in orthodontics. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2015;148(3):374-9.
2. Bozdog Z, Kurkcuoglu A, Ustidal A, Cam Y, OĞUZ Ö. Upper and lower lip soft tissue thicknesses differ in relation to age and sex. *grosos de los tejidos blandos de los labios superior e inferior difieren en relación con la edad y el sexo. International Journal of Morphology*. 2017;35(3).
3. Mohammed SA, Nissan LM, Taha SS. Soft tissue facial profile analysis of adult Iraqis with different classes of malocclusion. *Journal of Baghdad College of Dentistry*. 2013;25(4):151-9.
4. Santos RLd, Ruellas ACdO. Dentofacial characteristics of patients with Angle Class I and Class II malocclusions. *Dental Press Journal of Orthodontics*. 2012;17:46. e1-e7.
5. Ioi H, Nakata S, Nakasima A, Counts AL. Anteroposterior lip positions of the most-favored Japanese facial profiles. *American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics*. 2005;128(2):206-11.
6. Lee Y-J, Park J-T, Cha J-Y. Perioral soft tissue evaluation of skeletal Class II Division 1: A lateral cephalometric study. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2015;148(3):405-13.
7. HAMEED A, KHAN JI, IJAZ A. SOFT TISSUE FACIAL PROFILE ANALYSIS IN PATIENTS WITH CALSS I AND CLASS II SKELETAL PATTERN VISITING CHILDREN'S HOSPITAL, LAHORE. 2008.
8. Hashim HA, Albarakati SF. Cephalometric soft tissue profile analysis between two different ethnic groups: a comparative study. *The journal of contemporary dental practice*. 2005;4(2):60-73.
9. Kamak H, Celikoglu M. Facial soft tissue thickness among skeletal malocclusions: is there a difference? *Korean journal of orthodontics*. 2012;42(1):23.
10. Basciftci FA, Uysal T, Buyukerkmen A. Determination of Holdaway soft tissue norms in Anatolian Turkish adults. *American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics*. 2003;123(4):395-400.
11. Cooke MS, Orth D. Five-year reproducibility of natural head posture: a longitudinal study. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 1990;97(6):489-94.
12. Huggare J. Natural head position recording on frontal skull radiographs. *Acta Odontologica Scandinavica*. 1989;47(2):105-9.

13. Merrifield LL. The profile line as an aid in critically evaluating facial esthetics. *American journal of orthodontics*. 1966;52(11):804-22.
14. Ricketts RM. Esthetics, environment, and the law of lip relation. *American journal of orthodontics*. 1968;54(4):272-89.
15. Arnett GW, Gunson MJ. Facial planning for orthodontists and oral surgeons. *American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics*. 2004;126(3):290-5.
16. Kalha AS, Latif A, Govardhan S. Soft-tissue cephalometric norms in a South Indian ethnic population. *American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics*. 2008;133(6):876-81.
17. Sandham A. Repeatability of head posture recordings from lateral cephalometric radiographs. *British journal of orthodontics*. 1988;15(3):157-62.
18. Hoyte DA. Growth of the Cranial Base HHiH. *Fundamentals of Craniofacial Growth*: CRC Press; 2017. p. 257-334.
19. Uysal T, Yagci A, Basciftci FA, Sisman Y. Standards of soft tissue Arnett analysis for surgical planning in Turkish adults. *The European Journal of Orthodontics*. 2009;31(4):449-56.
20. Kang S-G, Lee Y-J, Park Y-G. A comparative study of soft tissue profile between Korean and Caucasian young adults under NHP. *Korean Journal of Orthodontics*. 2003;32:33-37.